

Okonkwo's 'Heart of Darkness' in Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*

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ABSTRACT:

What Okonkwo experiences first hand in *Things Fall Apart*, Marlow witnesses it from a distance. Achebe describes the cultural practices of his native place, whereas Conrad criticises the same practices from a white man's point of view. Achebe criticises and also tries to defend his native culture against a worldwide discourse of it being backward and uncivilised. Conrad draws a parallel line with the discourse but questions the inhuman atrocities committed by the colonizers in the name of 'white man's burden'. This paper tries to make a comparative study between Chinua Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* just to bring forth the difference in perspective of the writers; one representing the colonised and the other representing the colonizer.

KEYWORDS: Africa, colonised, coloniser; literature, culture, orientalism.

The Steamer toiled along slowly on the edge of a black and incomprehensible frenzy.

- Joseph Conrad, *Heart of Darkness* (1899)

Drums beat violently, and men leaped up and down in a frenzy.

- Chinua Achebe, *Things Fall Apart* (1958)

Both the books, Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* deal with colonialism in one way or the other, but their approach towards the notion of 'Colonialism' is strikingly different and that makes these two books the treasure of colonial study. Edward Said suggested that *Things Fall Apart* is unintelligible without *Heart of Darkness* (Said 288). In order to validate this paper, we need to do some research on the colonial period of Africa.

As a white writer, Joseph Conrad, in his *Heart of Darkness*, unfolds the horrific consequences of colonialism and is derisive of the entire process. He sheds light on the evils of colonialism and the European Capitalistic approach through Marlow's journey in the heart of darkness of Congo:

A slight clinking behind me made me turn my head. Six black men advanced in a file, toiling up the path. They walked erect and slow, balancing small baskets full

of earth on their heads, and the clink kept time with their footsteps. Black rags were wound round their loins, and the short ends behind waggled to and fro like tails. (Conrad 17)

On the other hand, the African author Chinua Achebe, through the story of Okonkwo in *Things Fall Apart*, criticizes Conrad's view from a colonized subject's perspective. Achebe's earliest and most well-known novel, *Things Fall Apart*, holds a unique place in African English literature. This manuscript, which has been hailed as the "archetypal modern African novel in English," is notable in that it opposes colonial persecution in Africa and offers a different postcolonial interpretation of pre-colonial African culture. (Lawtoo)

Achebe's novel depicts the advent of European colonizers in West Africa from the perspective of the inhabitants of Umuofia, who forms a community of Igbo speaking people.

In the novel, Okonkwo who is the protagonist of the story is seen as a very famous young man in all the nine villages of Umuofia. However, as the novel develops and white colonial masters begin to arrive in Umuofia in the disguise of missionaries, Okonkwo stands in protest of the change, but at the end is buried without respect or dignity and his fame is soon forgotten as he commits the greatest sin in Igbo religion- suicide.

One of the main reasons that *Things Fall Apart* was successful is because of its detailed descriptions of the authentic Igbo culture as seen from the perspective of its author. Achebe takes pride in his culture and is also critical about the ill practices of the Igbo society.

Achebe was the fifth of six children, and his family belonged to the Igbo tribe. British officials in charge of Nigeria persuaded his parents, Isaiah Okafor Achebe and Janet Ilegbunam, to convert to Christianity and give up their traditional beliefs. Despite being raised as a Christian, Achebe was nevertheless interested in the old Nigerian religion. (Encyclopedia of World Biography)

The society that has been depicted in *Things Fall Apart* is a well-structured and a modern guild and the inhabitants of the land are in no way in need of any other nation's participation in order to get themselves civilized. The Igbos have developed a democratic government. The Igbos are in some ways superior to those who come to convert them. Uchendu, for instance, is able to see that "what is good among one people is an abomination with others" (Achebe 46). Unlike the Europeans, the Igbos believe that it "is good that a man should worship the gods and spirits of his fathers" (Achebe 62), even if these gods are not the

Igbos' gods. While the European tradition allows men to fight their brothers over religion, the Igbo tradition forbids them to kill each other.

Achebe did not step back in criticizing the male dominance over the society and the indigenous way they lead their life. Ikemefuna, who was completely innocent, became a prey to his own adopted father, Okonkwo. *Things Fall Apart* does not simply repeat stereotypical images of Africa in order to conform to the discourse of the colonizer. There is no doubt that Achebe shows a male-governed society where women possess no power:

And when she returned, he beat her very heavily. In his anger he had forgotten that it was the Week of Peace. His first two wives ran out in great alarm pleading with him that it was the sacred week. (Achebe 9)

One can comfortably assert that Umuofia is the master setting or locale where the story of the *Things Fall Apart* is cast. Umuofia is a typical pre-colonial African rural settlement where the primary means of livelihood include farming, hunting, and gathering of forest resources. Invariably this indicates that the population of this rural area is bolstered by what nature offered (Dhar 98). Here, we get to see some glimpses of inhuman practices such as cannibalism:

In Umuofia's latest war he was the first to bring home a human head, that was his fifth head; and he was not an old man yet. On great occasions... he drank human head. (Achebe 3)

Sheer patriarchal authority over the land is being portrayed through this imagery of 'cannibalism'.

On the other hand, in *Heart of Darkness*, Conrad refers to Marlow's crew being made up of mostly cannibals- "One of my hungry and forbearing friends was sounding in the bows just below me" (Conrad 51). Cannibalism was one of the common aspects of African civilization. Cannibalism is the act or practice of human eating the flesh or internal organs of other human beings (Wikipedia). Many Amazonian, African, and Native American societies have traditionally practiced peaceful, cannibalistic mortuary rituals. Even in Defoe's masterpiece *Robinson Crusoe*, one of Crusoe's chief anxieties is about being eaten: "I expected every wave have swallowed us up" (Defoe 9). The cannibalistic tint is evident in the scene when Crusoe approaches Friday. However, throughout the whole story of *Heart of Darkness*, true cannibalism never takes place. The members of the crew were cannibals,

however in a totally different aspect. Serving more as a metaphor, the crew members are cannibals in the way that they overstep their limits of another human being. This would represent the Europeans overstepping their boundaries towards the natives.

Conrad, from the very beginning of his novella sees the Africans as an inferior race who are badly in need of modification. He is often considered to be an imperialist. To him, it's the superior race's responsibility to civilize them by taking over their land. As Conrad is cynical of the entire process, he makes use of several symbolic characters to accomplish this. The chief one being the shadowy and elusive Kurtz, who represents all the Europe: "All Europe contributed to the making of Kurtz" (Conrad 58).

'White Man's Burden' is the primary concern of the story of *Heart of Darkness*, the phrase, taken from Rudyard Kipling's poem of the same name. As a white-man Kurtz believes that the natives are in need of being civilized, improved and instructed in the European way of life. He sets out, before the novel starts, as an imperialist in the best traditional way to carry forward 'white man's burden'. He is a man who realizes the power of his own words, and his writings are 'marked by eloquence that obscures their horrifying message' (Bios). In the story, Kurtz stands for a normal man who realizes that he has to flourish in the interior of the Congo, and he can be a divine ruler over those primitive people and bring them towards the proverbial light and development. He can also be tagged as a 'hollow man'. Likewise, commenting on the famous final words of Kurtz before dying, Dianna Guadagnino writes:

The rape of the land, the consequences to the soul, the temptation of solitude, were a dark challenge, constructing moral dilemmas. Kurtz discovered 'He was empty inside.' His dying words, 'the horror, the horror' displays what he was inside at the end. (Guadagnino)

In the final scene, Marlow takes shelter under multiple lies in order to further his selfish agendas, rather the agenda of the Englishmen. Marlow tells Kurtz's fiancée that Kurtz's last words are only 'your name'. He does not really want to reveal the weaker aspects of colonialism in the name of 'white man's burden' and further allows Kurtz's darkness to live on within him. The Kenyan novelist Ngugi Wa Thiong'o regards the skulls stuck on poles outside Kurtz's abode at the Inner station to be a powerful indictment of colonialism. No African writer, he says, has created so ironic, apt and powerful an image:

ironic when one considers that Kurtz and many like him had come to 'civilize' the non-European world; apt when one recalls what they really did. (Conrad xxi-xxii)

This similar tone of burden is seen in *Things Fall Apart* too. The way English missionaries came, establishes churches, converted the natives into Christians, spread education, and is very clear that the natives are nothing but a hefty burden to them whom they have to civilize. The Europeans had to go preaching to them from house to house to get them to come to their shine. The total sum of these endeavors is that they first attract the *efulefus*, the *osus* and the marginalized in Umuofian clan.

Conrad not only reveals the positive aspects of white-colonialism, he also exhibits their evil practices towards the natives. Ivory was the profitable trade which was found by the Belgian trading company when Belgian king Leopold II ruled the Congo. It was useless to the natives but very valuable to the white men because of its usage in ornament manufacturing. Thus the objective of white men was to indulge in the exploitation and brutality in order to draw out ivory from the natives. The Europeans did not care about the health and working conditions of the natives as long as they are productive. The natives were mostly naked and were made to move like ants-

I could see every rib, the joints of their limbs were like knots in a rope; each had an iron collar on his neck, and all were connected together with a chain... (Conrad 17)

Through the actions of the Europeans, the natives are made fearful in order to protect their lives and the lives of the families, they submit to the will of the foreigners. Kurtz, in the story, believes that the ivory is only for him. He states: "My ivory... my intended, my ivory. My station, my river, my-" (Conrad 57)

Though, Achebe's novel is devoid of such direct cruelties, this flavor is evident in another colonial masterpiece *Shooting an Elephant*, by George Orwell. Orwell like Conrad in *Heart of Darkness* presents the moral dilemmas of the imperialist. In order to retain his superiority and to keep his title 'Sahib' intact, he had to shoot the elephant, which was not merely an animal, but the imagery of 'stricken, shrunken, immensely old' countries.

As for the job I was doing, I hated it more bitterly than I can perhaps make clear. In a job like that you see the dirty work of Empire at close quarters. The wretched prisoners huddling in the stinking cages of the lock-ups...I did not even know that

the British Empire is dying, still less did I know that it is a great deal better than the younger empires... (Orwell 5)

Imperialistic dilemma was one of the key ingredients of Conrad. Although he did not fail in depicting the ups and downs of white colonialism, he did not go beyond criticism. *Heart of Darkness* is criticised by Achebe in his essay *Image of Africa*, in which he also labels Conrad a virulent racist. Achebe claims that Conrad denies Africans' "human expression" and even robs them of language. Africa is portrayed as "a foil to Europe"—a region of negations that is both far away and faintly familiar—in contrast with which Europe's own position of spiritual grace would be demonstrated. Conrad's depiction of Africa as "the other world," the antithesis of Europe and so of civilization, according to him, is the consequence of his "residue of antipathy to black people." Achebe credits Conrad for this. Achebe's quotation that follows serves as an effective example of his viewpoint:

that of my observation should be quite clear by now, namely that Joseph Conrad was a thoroughgoing racist. That this simple truth is glossed over in criticisms of his work is due to the fact that white racism against Africa is such a normal way of thinking that its manifestations go completely unremarked. (Achebe 6)

In his insightful book *Culture and Imperialism*, Edward Said vigorously defended Conrad by pointing out that *Heart of Darkness's* politics and aesthetics are, in a sense, imperialist, which in the final years of the nineteenth century seemed to be simultaneously an aesthetic, politics, and even epistemology inevitable and unavoidable:

Conrad's genius allowed him to realize that the ever-present darkness could be colonized or illuminated - *Heart of Darkness* is full of references to the mission *civilisatrice*, to benevolent as well as cruel schemes to bring light to the dark places and peoples of this world by acts of will and deployments of power. (Said 56-57)

Likewise, we find what Okonkwo experiences first hand in *Things Fall Apart*, Marlow witnesses it from a distance. Achebe describes the cultural practices of his native place, whereas Conrad criticises the same practices from a white man's point of view. Achebe criticises and also tries to defend his native culture against a worldwide discourse of it being backward and uncivilized. Conrad draws a parallel line with the discourse but questions the inhuman atrocities committed by the colonizers in the name of 'white man's burden'.

Therefore, it becomes evident that Okonkwo and Kurtz become two sides of the same coin- Colonialism.

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